

The Search for Multi-Functional Composite Material and Structure
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Composite Applications

- Fatigue
- Interlaminar Shear
- Micro-Cracking
- Impact
- Thermal & Electrical properties

Advanced Energy Solutions

- Ultra Fast Charging
- High Power Density
- Long Life (lower Cost)
- Temperature Stability
- Safe

NAWASTitch® – 100 Trillion VACNTs per m² - vertically-aligned CNTs provide Z-axis reinforcement of plies, localised to areas of stress.

Hybrid nanocomposites combine the strength and stiffness of CFRP with targeted toughening between plies, 0.2% aerial weight after cure

No Nawastitch at interfaces

Fracture propagates along interface

Nawastitch at interfaces

Fracture is driven into ply and stops propagating

- ✓ Impact damage tolerance (+900%)
- ✓ Shear fatigue (+5x-40x)
- ✓ ILSS (+20-30%)
- ✓ ILT (+25%)
- ✓ CAI (+15-50%)
- ✓ Compression (+10%)
- ✓ No negative deltas against baselines.

Impact Fatigue Damage Progression (3.3 J/mm)

Impact “fatigue” is conducted by hitting a single point multiple times at low energy, illustrating the growth of impact damage over time

Testing at -195C (-320F)

H2 Tank Testing, Cyclic Strain / Stress Testing at -195.8C (-320F)

← Baseline laminate

Visible Micro Cracking
(microcracks on the NAWA Panel are smaller and fewer in number, also the microcracks on the NAWA Panel did not link up)

← NAWASTitch VACNT laminate

Benefits of NAWASTitch

- 50% less microcracking on 45 degree plys
- 20% less microcracking on 90 degree Plys
- Micro cracking starts at 20% higher strain levels

The following results were observed in the rain erosion tests at certain time markers test conducted at 300 mph:

- 30 minutes: erosion was observed on the control sample but no damage was observed on the panel with VACNTs on the surface
- 60 minutes: the VACNT panel started to show some minor pitting damage on the surface
- 180 minutes: the VACNT panel showed less than half the damage of the control panel
- Throughout all the tests the VACNT panel showed less damage than the control panel

- VACNT's electrical & Thermal properties / heating rate very stable and consistent

Zoned Heating Capability
310F = 154C

24 hour test at 52C (125F)
Power usage at 18.6A

NAWA Anti Icing / Deicing Patent in Process

Structural health monitoring

NAWASTitch Cured Panel

Multiple Zoned heating

Typical Electrical Double Layer superCapacitor (EDLC)

Carbon fiber reinforced structural supercapacitor

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